

ISCCRO'18

Book of Abstracts

of the ISCCRO -
International Statistical Conference in Croatia

Opatija, Croatia, 10-11 May 2018

CONFERENCE TOPIC:

*„New Advances in Statistical Methods Applications for
a Better World “*

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Vol. 2, No. 1

Editors-in-Chief:

Ksenija Dumičić, Nataša Erjavec, Mirjana Pejić Bach, Berislav Žmuk

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The International Statistical Conference in Croatia (**The Second ISCCRO'18**) has been organised by **Croatian Statistical Association**

The ISCCRO'18 General Chair: Marko Kristof, Vice-President, Croatian Statistical Association & Director General at Croatian Bureau of Statistics, Zagreb, Croatia

The ISCCRO'18 Conference Program Chair: Ksenija Dumičić, President, Croatian Statistical Association & Univ. of Zagreb, Faculty of Economics and Business, Dept. of Statistics, Zagreb, Croatia

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The **ISCCRO'18** Conference has been organised under the **patronage** of the **Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Croatia**.

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Focus and Scope of the ISCCRO Conference

The ISCCRO - International Statistical Conference in Croatia is a scientific event in the area of statistics organized for the first time by the **Croatian Statistical Association (CSA)** in 2016 (ISCCRO'16) in Zagreb, Croatia. It became a biannual event important not only for Croatia, but also internationally, attracting scientists and professionals in statistics and related fields from many countries. Invited people gather both data producers and data users, scientists and professionals, educators and students. One should attend this international conference because of the range of theoretical and practical statistical topics, discussed by wider audience, which makes this conference unique in Croatia. Therefore, the conference ISCCRO has been the best place for sharing and exchanging information and building networks, for both domestic and international statisticians, where each learns from the other.

The Second International Statistical Conference in Croatia - ISCCRO'18, with the topic: **"New Advances in Statistical Methods Applications for a Better World"**, was held from the 10th to the 11th May 2018 in Opatija, Croatia. The conference, covering statistical and related cross and multi-disciplinary fields, topics and areas, provides a platform for international networking and exchange of ideas on various aspects of theory and applications of statistics and related professional and scientific areas.

At the ISCCRO'18 in Opatija 188 authors, coming from 19 countries and Croatia, gave 100 submissions for presentation, half of them as Abstract Only and half of them as Full Papers, split in a variety of sessions in two parallel lines during two conference days of presentations, four of them being Invited Lectures. *Croatian Statistical Association* co-organized five Special Sessions, as follows: *Spreading out Official Statistics in the Digital World*, organized by Maja Pekeč from Croatian Bureau of Statistics; *Econometric Modelling for Fiscal Policy Making in European Union Countries*, chaired by Assistant Professor Irena Palić, PhD, University of Zagreb, Faculty of Economics and Business, Zagreb, Croatia; *Economic and Social Effects of Demographic Trends*, chaired by Professor Ana Štambuk, PhD, University of Rijeka, Faculty of Economics, Rijeka, Croatia; *Modern Techniques for Handling Large Spatial Data*, organized by Professor Taps Maiti, PhD, Michigan State University, East Lansing, Michigan, USA & Croatian Statistical Association; and *Quantitative Analysis for Faster Development of the South East European Countries*, organized by Associate Professor Blagica Novkovska, PhD, from University of Tourism and Management in Skopje, Republic of Macedonia. Croatian Statistical Association organized the Special Session *Young Statisticians in Action*, too.

The conference hosted the authors from Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Republic of Macedonia, Russian Federation, Poland, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, South Africa, Sweden, Ukraine, United Kingdom and USA.

The **Book of Abstracts of the ISCCRO – International Statistical Conference in Croatia** (Online ISSN 2584-3850; Print ISSN 1849-9864), contains four Plenary Speech abstracts and 96 contributed abstracts of the talks presented at the ISCCRO'18 Conference. Besides that, the **Proceedings of the ISCCRO - International Statistical Conference in Croatia**, published after The Second ISCCRO'18, held in Opatija, Croatia, 10-11 May 2018, Volume 2, No. 1, 2018, Electronical ISSN: 1849-9872, includes 24 selected double-blind peer reviewed conference papers.

The International Scientific Program Committee, which is the Editorial Board of the ISCCRO'18, includes 118 scientists and professionals, from all over the World, 60% of them being from outside of Croatia. The ISCCRO'18 International Organizing Committee is comprised of the statisticians from four countries: Croatia, Serbia, Republic of Macedonia and Slovenia, which is the proof of the international importance of the ISCCRO conference.

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Exploring connections between researchers and ideas in the European Hardwoods Innovation Alliance using two-mode social network analysis

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Abstract:

Two-mode social network analysis (SNA) can be applied to data that consists of two sets of units, from analysing persons and societies to authors and papers. The objective of this paper is to evaluate the possibilities of this approach for the analysis of connections between researchers and their future research ideas based on survey data. As a case study we used the data of the 2016 membership survey of the European Hardwoods Innovation Alliance, a transnational collaboration of experts in wood science and related fields. They were asked to propose research programmes dedicated to the sustainable, innovative, added-value use of hardwood species in Europe. 199 different contributors from 38 countries participated and provided 219 validated innovation ideas that were classified into 17 different topic categories. Based on two-mode SNA we found that most ideas belong only to one topic, while a small number of researchers suggested research programmes on more than one topic and thus represent intergroup nodes in the network. However, we also identified researchers and topics isolated from the larger group of respondents. The case study highlights the suitability of SNA as a tool for the exploration and visualisation of research communities. The spotted groups, whose members do not necessarily know each other, suggest an interest for potential exchange and collaboration, which is a basis for the formation of new research consortia in innovative fields.

Keywords: innovation, research mapping and clustering, social network analysis.

JEL code: D85, O32.

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